

Among the compounds screened for antitubercular activity **3a**, **c**, **g**, **4a**, **c** and **d** were found to inhibit the human strain H₃₇R_V of *M. tuberculosis* at 10 µg ml⁻¹ concentration and have comparable activity with streptomycin. Rest of the compounds showed activity at 100 µg ml⁻¹ concentration. Compounds **3a**, **b**, **c**, **4a**, **b**, **c** and **j** (79–88% inhibition) showed comparable activity with griseofulvin (80–88% inhibition) against *A. helianthi*.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Toshniwal CL0301 apparatus in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR 8000 spectrophotometer and PMR spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a EM 390 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel G. All compounds showed satisfactory elemental analysis.

6,7-Diphenyl-3,5-disubstituted-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazines (3a): A mixture of **2a** (0.01 mol) and benzoin (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was heated to get a clear solution. To this hot solution, 2*N* KOH solution (2 ml) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h. On cooling the mixture, a light yellow precipitate that separated out was dried and crystallized from aqueous ethanol: **3a** (70%), m.p. 284° (Found: C, 71.10; H, 3.99; N, 14.73. C₂₈H₁₉N₅OS calcd. for: C, 71.03; H, 4.01; N, 14.79%), ν_{max} 3050 (aromatic C–H), 1660 (C=O), 1630 (C=N), 1610 (C=C), 1515 (C–N), 1070, 700 cm⁻¹ (C–S), absence of band for SH; δ 8.1–7.3 (15H, m, ArH), 8.85–8.7 (4H, m, pyridyl), **3c** (74%), 246° (Found: C, 66.18; H, 3.46; N, 13.74. C₂₈H₁₈ClN₅OS calcd. for: C, 66.27; H, 3.55; N, 13.80%), ν_{max} 3060 (aromatic C–H), 1660 (C=O), 1620 (C=N), 1605 (C=C), 1510 (C–N), 1070, 700 cm⁻¹ (C–S), absence of band for SH; δ 8.0–7.3 (14H, m, ArH), 8.8–8.7 (4H, m, pyridyl). Similarly, other compounds (yields 65–83%) were prepared and crystallized from aqueous ethanol: **3b**, m.p. 266°; **d**, 188°; **e**, 236°; **f**, 268°; **g**, 244°; **h**, 212°; **i**, 180°; **j**, 216°; **k**, 280°; **l**, 262°.

3,4-Disubstituted-7(H)-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazinones (4c): A mixture of **2c** (0.01 mol), chloroacetic acid (0.01 mol) and fused sodium acetate (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 12 h, then

cooled and poured into cold water. The resulting solid was dried and crystallized from ethanol: **4a** (80%), m.p. 220° (Found: C, 57; H, 3.2; N, 20.66. C₁₆H₁₁N₅O₂S calcd. for: C, 56.97; H, 3.26; N, 20.77%), ν_{max} 3050 (aromatic C–H), 1690 (C=O of thiadiazinone ring), 1660 (C=O of C₆H₅NCO), 1620 (C=N), 1610 (C=C), 1515 (C–N), 1050, 700 cm⁻¹ (C–S); δ 2.5 (2H, s, CH₂), 8.1–7.4 (5H, m, ArH), 8.85–8.65 (4H, m, pyridyl); **4c** (78%), 174° (Found: C, 51.82; H, 2.59; N, 18.90. C₁₆H₁₀N₅O₂SCl calcd. for: C, 51.75; H, 2.69; N, 18.86%), ν_{max} 3070 (aromatic C–H), 1690 (C=O of thiadiazinone ring), 1660 (C=O of C₆H₅NCO), 1625 (C=N), 1610 (C=C), 1520 (C–N), 1050, 710 cm⁻¹ (C–S); δ 2.5 (2H, s, CH₂), 8.1–7.4 (4H, m, ArH), 8.75–8.65 (4H, m, pyridyl). Similarly, other compounds (yields 70–85%) were prepared and crystallized from ethanol: **4b**, m.p. 244°; **d**, 196°; **e**, 280°; **f**, 220°; **g**, 276°; **h**, 237°; **i**, 258°; **j**, 273°; **k**, 258°; **l**, 236°.

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